

ENVELOPE FOLLOWING VIA CASCADED EXPONENTIAL SMOOTHERS FOR LOW-DISTORTION PEAK LIMITING AND MAXIMISATION

Dario Sanfilippo

Independent
Catania, Italy

sanfilippodario@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we discuss the implementation of look-ahead peak limiters using exponential envelope followers and their deployment in multi-band loudness maximisation. Particularly, the limiter’s amplitude profiling algorithm uses cascaded one-pole filters to improve derivative continuity and reduce convolution artefacts when multiplying the input signal by the attenuation gain as shown in a total harmonic distortion analysis. The maximiser algorithm allows for two independent maximisation modalities that can be combined: an RMS-based dynamic normalisation of each band with controllable depth to reach equal power, and a global maximisation gain that boosts the individual bands by the same amount. An open-source FAUST implementation of these algorithms is available on Github at the links: <https://github.com/dariosanfilippo/limiterStereo> and <https://github.com/dariosanfilippo/maximiser>.

1. INTRODUCTION

Limiting is a form of dynamic range processing that operates when a signal exceeds a certain amplitude threshold forcing it within boundaries, while it leaves it unaltered when the signal is below the limit. Even though this task can be realised effectively through a clipping function, introducing little or no distortion is key for the processor to perform adequately in a music and audio context. Look-ahead processing is a technique in dynamic range compression and limiting that allows for gain signals to be applied smoothly, hence reducing the distortion introduced by the process. It consists of delaying the input signal by a small amount so that the attenuation curve can reach the target values gradually [1].

Essentially, envelope profiling for the computation of the gain attenuation signal can be performed using two methods: finite impulse response (FIR) filtering, such as rectangular moving average filters, or infinite impulse response (IIR) filtering, such as one-pole low-pass filters (exponentially-weighted averaging units). Both approaches have unique characteristics that can be desirable depending on the specific use case; arguably, the most relevant difference is that FIR systems can reach the target value exactly within a specified period, while IIR systems converge at arbitrary rates. Furthermore, the exponential growth and decay of IIR systems are perceptually more natural compared to the FIR ones.¹ For the reasons above, an FIR system is suitable for brick-wall limiting, that is, limiters that guarantee a strict amplitude boundary for the output signal, whereas IIR systems are more appropriate for the musical context due to their natural-sounding behaviour.

In the following sections, we will discuss the key building blocks for the amplitude profiling: the peak-holder and the envelope smoothing units. Then, we will provide an overshooting and total harmonic distortion (THD) analysis for the peak limiter under common settings and broad-spectrum test signals. Finally, we will show how the peak limiter can be deployed in maximisation units through multi-band processing.

2. PEAK LIMITER DESIGN

2.1. Peak Detection Via Cascaded Peak-Holders

The principle of a peak limiter is to detect the amplitude profile of the incoming signal and compute the gain values that scale the input down if above a threshold, or leave it unaltered if below it. For this design, we rely on peak amplitude profiling, using peak-holders. A peak-holder is a system that outputs the input absolute value if larger than or equal to the current out. Otherwise, a timer is set and the system holds the current output for the desired period, after which the current output is updated with the absolute value of the input. The function described above can be used to create a staircase signal tracking the amplitude peaks of the input. The resulting signal can then be smoothed out with exponential smoothers having specific attack and release times to obtain the gain attenuation and control the output amplitude. We will get back to exponential smoothers shortly.

We set the hold period of the peak holder and the look-ahead delay equal to the attack time of the exponential smoother. This way, we allow the smoothers to converge to the target value and synchronise the peaks of the attenuation with those of the input signal. Additionally, besides the attack and release parameters, the limiter has a hold time that extends the hold period of the peak detection section beyond the attack time; this can be particularly useful to improve THD at low frequencies. If we use a single peak-holder, we are not able to detect secondary peaks that appear within the hold period. We can address this problem by cascading N peak-holders, each of them having a hold period that is $1/N$ of the full hold period. This allows for secondary peaks that appear after $1/N$ of the period to be detected. For the design of this limiter, specifically, we use eight cascaded peak-holders, which appear to work well for most cases considering that the non-detected peaks fall within the attenuation curve in the release phase. If the release time is considerably larger than the attack time, as it is often the case, essentially all non-detected peaks will be covered by the release curve and the overshooting will be minimal. See Figures 1, 2, 3, 4, and section 2.4 below. We call the output of the final stage of the peak detection:

$$p_{a,h}[n], \tag{1}$$

¹https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~jos/mdft/Why_Exponentials_Important.html

Figure 1: Edge case for secondary non-detected peaks at 90% of the primary one.

Figure 3: Edge case for secondary non-detected peaks at 99.9% of the primary one with five times longer release time.

Figure 2: Effectiveness of cascaded peak-holders to detect secondary peaks.

Figure 4: Edge case for secondary non-detected peaks at 99.9%: close-up.

2.2. Envelope Following Via Cascaded Exponential Smoothers

Exponential smoothers can be implemented via simple recursive equations representing one-pole systems of the form:

$$s[n] = x[n] + \alpha(s[n-1] - x[n]). \quad (2)$$

The α coefficient determines the pole position of the recursive system, which controls the growth and decay rates.² For our design, we use a time constant that is $2\pi\tau$, and we can calculate the coefficient α as:

$$\alpha = e^{-\frac{2\pi T}{\tau}}, \quad (3)$$

where T is the sampling period and τ is the time, in seconds, for the step response to reach $1 - e^{-2\pi}$. Single one-pole smoothers for dynamic range compression are discussed extensively in [2]. Envelope following systems with separate attack and release parameters can be implemented as series or parallel configurations of one-pole filters. Giannoulis et al. (2012) investigate branching and

decoupled designs for envelope following and improve the THD of the dynamic range processors by smoothing out the transition between attack and release sections: since multiplication in the time-domain corresponds to convolution in the frequency-domain, it is vital that the attenuation curve has continuous derivatives to reduce distortion. However, the attack phase of single one-pole envelope followers shows a sharp onset. We can address this problem by cascading M envelope following sections to guarantee continuity in the derivatives up to order $M - 1$, hence producing smooth curves even when transitioning between attack and release phases. The individual envelope following units that we use are branching sections of the following kind:

$$s[n] = \begin{cases} x[n] + \alpha_a(s[n-1] - x[n]), & \text{if } x[n] > s[n-1] \\ x[n] + \alpha_r(s[n-1] - x[n]), & \text{if } x[n] \leq s[n-1] \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where α_a and α_r are, respectively, the attack and release sections coefficients. Cascading two or more one-pole filters at the same cut-off results in an overall shifted cut-off at the output stage. [3] suggests a coefficient correction formula to maintain an atten-

²https://ccrma.stanford.edu/~jos/fp/One_Pole.html

uation of $1/\sqrt{2}$ at cut-off. For M cascaded sections, the cut-off multiplier is given by:

$$C_M = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^{1/M} - 1}}. \quad (5)$$

Similarly, cascading several one-pole smoothers affects the growth and decay rates, which we can correct using (5) to obtain consistent behaviour when deploying several one-pole systems in series. The calculation of the coefficients for the individual smoothing sections becomes:

$$\alpha_M = e^{\frac{-2\pi T C_M}{\tau}}. \quad (6)$$

The transfer function of the combined sections is:

$$\left(\frac{1 - \alpha_M}{1 - \alpha_M z^{-1}} \right)^M. \quad (7)$$

Since the coefficient is the same for each section, cascading M one-pole smoothers only requires $2M$ extra sums and M extra multiplies. We call the output of the final stage of M cascaded one-pole smoothers:

$$s_{a,h,r,M}[n]. \quad (8)$$

Figure 5: Step response of cascaded exponential smoothers.

2.3. Attenuation Gain Computation

As discussed in [4], since the input signal must remain unaltered when its peaks are below the threshold, the computation of the attenuation signal requires a \min or \max function to clip the gain at a neutral level when needed. These clipping functions produce a discontinuity in the derivative of the signal while transitioning from the neutral to the attenuating values and vice versa. If l is the limiter ceiling, one option to compute the attenuation gain is:

$$g_{a,h,r,l,M}[n] = \min \left(1, \frac{l}{s_{a,h,r,M}[n]} \right), \quad (9)$$

which must be smoothed out subsequently to remove any sharp edges in the signal. Alternatively, we can clip at the stage of peak detection, before applying the smoothing processing, leading to:

$$q_{a,h,l}[n] = \max(l, p_{a,h}[n]), \quad (10)$$

Figure 6: Step response of cascaded exponential smoothers: close-up of the attack phase.

Figure 7: Step response of cascaded exponential smoothers: close-up of the attack-to-release transition.

and use the resulting signal as input for the first stage of the cascaded smoothing. Besides no longer requiring a smoothing filter for the final gain, a key difference with this approach is that the envelope smoothers, when transitioning between neutral and attenuating gain values, charge from – and discharge to – the ceiling threshold rather than the current peak, hence using the attack and release times more effectively. See Figure 8 and 9 for a comparison. Also note that, assuming $l > 0$, there is no need to check for division by 0. Then, the attenuation signal is:

$$g_{a,h,r,l,M}[n] = \frac{l}{s_{a,h,r,M}[n]}. \quad (11)$$

2.4. Overshooting and Total Harmonic Distortion Analysis

The attack phase step response of M τ -constant cascaded exponential filters, that is, filters that charge by $1 - e^{-1}$ at a specified time $t \geq 0$, can be determined using the following closed-form equation:

Figure 8: Comparison of envelope followers for gain computation: transitions between neutral and attenuating values with a 0 dB ceiling. Attack and release times are .01 and .05 second; 0 hold time. Note that the input is delayed by the attack time to synchronise the gain outputs.

Figure 9: Gain computation comparison: close-up of the attack phase.

$$A_{\tau_a, M}(t) = 1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_a}} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \frac{\left(\frac{t}{\tau_a}\right)^m}{m!}, \quad (12)$$

where τ_a is the response time in seconds.³ We can extend the equation to describe a $2\pi\tau$ -constant system and include the coefficient correction from (5). We have that:

$$A_{2\pi\tau_a, C_M}(t) = 1 - e^{-\frac{2\pi t C_M}{\tau_a}} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \frac{\left(\frac{2\pi t C_M}{\tau_a}\right)^m}{m!}. \quad (13)$$

Coefficient-corrected series IIR smoothers build up more slowly but converge more quickly. The envelope follower for the proposed limiter uses four cascaded branching sections such as the

³<https://signalsmith-audio.co.uk/writing/2022/limiter>

ones described in (4). From (13), we can see that the peak of the attack step response of the amplitude profiler is:

$$K_4 = A_{2\pi\tau_a, C_4}(\tau_a) \approx 0.99966855948853062. \quad (14)$$

Hence, for the attack phase, we can predict a maximum overshooting in dB of:

$$|20 \log(K_4)| \approx 0.002879332894, \quad (15)$$

which is independent of the attack time. The release phase step response at time $t > \tau_a$ is:

$$R_{2\pi\tau_r, C_M}(t) = K_M e^{-\frac{2\pi(t-\tau_a)C_M}{\tau_r}} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \frac{\left(\frac{2\pi(t-\tau_a)C_M}{\tau_r}\right)^m}{m!}, \quad (16)$$

where τ_r is the release response time. Considering the worst-case for the non-detected secondary peaks discussed in 2.1, we can calculate the maximum overshooting in the release phase using:

$$R_{2\pi\tau_r, C_M}\left(\tau_a + \frac{\tau_a}{N}\right), \quad (17)$$

where N is the number of cascaded peak-holder sections at $1/N$ hold time. In limiters, it is common for the release time to be considerably larger than the attack time. If we choose τ_r as a factor of τ_a , we make the overshooting dependent only on the factor itself. For example, by setting τ_r to twice, five times, or ten times τ_a , we guarantee the overshooting to be below the following dB values regardless of the attack time:

$$\left|20 \log\left(R_{2\pi\tau_{2a}, C_4}\left(\tau_a + \frac{\tau_a}{8}\right)\right)\right| \approx 0.1217966284, \quad (18)$$

$$\left|20 \log\left(R_{2\pi\tau_{5a}, C_4}\left(\tau_a + \frac{\tau_a}{8}\right)\right)\right| \approx 0.00750023597, \quad (19)$$

$$\left|20 \log\left(R_{2\pi\tau_{10a}, C_4}\left(\tau_a + \frac{\tau_a}{8}\right)\right)\right| \approx 0.003213466763. \quad (20)$$

Studies show loudness just noticeable difference to be approximately 0.1 dB or higher [5]. Based on that information, we can scale down the output of the limiter by the maximum overshooting values to guarantee a clip-free output and a negligible loudness loss for settings where the release time is twice the attack time or higher. Alternatively, we can deploy a 0 dB hard-clipping function at the output of the limiter and maximum ceiling to avoid loudness losses while increasing the overall THD by minimal amounts, i.e.: 0.5 % or less for release times that are twice the attack time or higher. Although cascaded exponential smoothers are not suitable for brick-wall limiting and clip-free outputs at maximal loudness levels, the THD measurements in Figure 10 show a significant reduction in the overall degradation caused by ring modulation distortion while the loudness loss is essentially imperceptible. The final output of the limiter is:

$$y_{a,h,r,l,M}[n] = g_{a,h,r,l,M}[n]x[n - a/T], \quad (21)$$

which shows that the limiter introduces a delay in the signal that is equal to the attack time. Multi-channel limiters can be realised by feeding the peak detection unit with the maximum peak of the individual channels to compute a global attenuation signal that applies to all channels.

Figure 10: Total harmonic distortion comparison between single, two, three, and four cascaded exponential smoothers. The input test signal is a sinusoid at 0 dB. The limiter’s pre-gain is 60 dB, the attack time is .001 second, the hold time is 0, the release time is .1 second, and the output ceiling is 0 dB. THD values are calculated every quarter octave starting from 20 Hz. Specifically, the measurement is carried out as the ratio between the RMS of the delay-compensated input and output signals difference, and the RMS of the input signal.

3. LOUDNESS MAXIMISER DESIGN

3.1. Multi-Band Processing

Look-ahead limiters alone can provide significant loudness increase when operating with boosted signals, although degradation and background noise are likely to emerge when the amplification is particularly high. One way to address this problem is multi-band processing, that is, the amplification and limiting of individual spectral bands so that artefacts can be reduced by distributing the stress of the boosting evenly: some spectral bands in a signal are typically weaker than others and can be amplified more before degradation becomes significant.

This maximiser’s implementation uses an eight-way Linkwitz-Riley fourth-order crossover [6], which is available in FAUST’s Standard Library. In this early implementation of the maximiser, the bands spacing is fixed with a single-octave width starting from 40 Hz. Furthermore, this version has global parameters for all of the bands although future improvements may deploy individual band settings for more versatile configurations. Each band is connected to a limiter, and their outputs are summed into a final limiter stage that controls the output ceiling. Particularly, the limiters connected to each band have a fixed ceiling of 0 dB, while the final output ceiling can be adjusted to arbitrary values. Thus, the overall delay of the maximiser is twice the combined attack and hold times. Also note that, while the release parameter can be set independently for each band in future versions of the maximiser, the attack and hold times must be the same for all bands to preserve phase alignment and a flat magnitude response when summing out the bands.

Figure 11: Limiter stereo UI.

3.2. Maximisation Modalities

Essentially, the processor has two modalities for multi-band maximisation that can operate in conjunction. On one hand, the maximiser offers the possibility to dynamically normalise the bands so that they have the same level approximately; on a sample-by-sample basis, the RMS of the loudest band is the reference value used to calculate a gain factor to bring all bands at the same level. The RMS calculation is carried out with $2\pi\tau$ -constant one-pole filters and a one-second response time. Connected to this feature is a normalisation depth parameter that sets the maximum gain amount for normalisation. Assuming that the input signal without amplification is below 0 dB, the dynamical normalisation process does not set the limiters of the individual bands into an operational mode; hence, this process is free from degradation except for the limiting provided by the final limiter stage when the sum of the individual bands exceeds the ceiling. Alternatively, the maximisation can be performed by applying a gain amplification to the input signal, hence boosting all of the bands equally. The main difference is that dynamical normalisation provides maximum individual amplification with minimum degradation. On the other hand, the global gain amplification results in higher degradation for the predominant bands while keeping the overall spectral weights closer to the original signal.

Figure 12: Maximiser mono UI.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have discussed the implementation of look-ahead peak limiters deploying cascaded exponential smoothers for envelope following. Besides the natural-sounding behaviour of exponential smoothers, measurements show that implementing cascaded sections of one-pole envelope followers improves the THD when used in look-ahead limiting. Furthermore, IIR filters offer an alternative to moving average filters and reduce memory requirements, while calculations show that the overshooting of cascaded IIR filters is negligible for most musical applications. Finally, the paper shows an implementation of the peak limiter design in multi-band maximisers offering two non-exclusive modalities: dynamical band normalisation, for low-degradation maximisation, and homogeneous signal boosting to preserve, to some extent, the original bands weights. Future work on the limiter will include the implementation of adaptive mechanisms for automatic adjustments of the parameters and optimal THD and recovery time. We will include the possibility to switch between amplitude profiling in the linear or log (dB) domains. Furthermore, the author will explore a creative applications of the limiter in his work on music feedback systems, specifically using the limiter with non-standard parameter settings as a stability processor in self-oscillating systems.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank Geraint "Signalsmith" Luff for providing inspiration and insights during the development of this work.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] Udo Zölzer, Xavier Amatriain, Daniel Arfib, Jordi Bonada, Giovanni De Poli, Pierre Dutilleux, Gianpaolo Evangelista, Florian Keiler, Alex Loscos, Davide Rocchesso, et al., *DAFX-Digital audio effects*, John Wiley & Sons, 2002.
- [2] Dimitrios Giannoulis, Michael Massberg, and Joshua D Reiss, "Digital dynamic range compressor design—a tutorial and analysis," *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 399–408, 2012.
- [3] Vadim Zavalishin, "The art of va filter design," *Native Instruments, Berlin, Germany*, 2012.
- [4] Perttu Hämäläinen, "Smoothing of the control signal without clipped output in digital peak limiters," in *International Conference on Digital Audio Effects (DAFx)*, Hamburg, Germany, 2002, NordiCHI, pp. 195–198, DAFx.
- [5] Scott G. Norcross, Gilbert A. Soulodre, and Michel C. Lavoie, "The subjective loudness of typical program material," *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, October 2003.
- [6] Siegfried H Linkwitz, "Active crossover networks for noncoincident drivers," *Journal of the Audio Engineering Society*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 2–8, 1976.